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Modelling the effect of misalignment in conventional and non-conventional deep drawing tools for more resilient cup production

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Abstract. Deep cup-shaped products of cold rolled sheet metal are produced by multiple deep drawing stages. Adjusting the tooling during production for a product or material change can only be carried out by appropriately trained and experienced employees. One reason for the complexity of the tool change is the static overdetermination of the tool system which leaves no degree of freedom for the punch. Therefore, the alignment of the punch to the die has to be very precise. Coaxial misalignment induces changes in wall thickness distributions concerning the circumference of the cup, leading to defects. To reduce the effort for reconfiguration, a tool concept for a deep drawing tool for circular parts is presented, which can compensate the inaccuracies in the alignment with guidance near the forming zone. In this finite element (FE) simulation study, the effects of coaxial misalignment and alignment of the punch and the die on both tools are modelled. The results of the wall thickness distribution is then compared and evaluated. Furthermore, the validity of the results is determined through a experiment on a deep drawing demonstrator. The approach offers the potential for a reduction in both set-up time and the number of defective cups with deviating wall thicknesses, which results in a more resilient production of cup-shaped products.

1. Introduction

The rapid onset of the COVID-19 pandemic precipitated widespread disruptions across industrial production. These disruptions have led to persistent bottlenecks in labor availability and material supply chains, alongside significant shifts in product demand patterns [1]. Such uncertainties have highlighted the critical need for resilient and reconfigurable manufacturing systems at macro, meso, and micro levels [2]. A resilient system is comprised of six phases, three of them are: prevention, mitigation, and adaptation and learning [3].

In the context of deep drawing processes for the production of cup-shaped components from cold-rolled sheet metal, resilience is often limited by the need for frequent and precise tool adjustments during product or material changes. These adjustments, particularly in multi-stage forming operations, demand substantial experience and expertise [4]. A key challenge arises from the static indeterminacy of conventional tooling systems, which necessitates highly accurate alignment of the punch relative to the die [5]. This lack of compliance limits the system's ability to adapt quickly, thereby reducing flexibility and resilience in production.

This work introduces a non-conventional deep drawing tool concept, implemented as a statically determined laboratory demonstrator. The study investigates the impact of coaxial misalignment between the punch and die through a finite element (FE) simulation approach for cold-rolled steel (DC05) cup production.

2. Non-conventional deep drawing tool too strength resilience

Guidance systems in conventional deep drawing tools, such as those using pillars or heel blocks, are typically statically indeterminate [5]. This means that multiple constraint reactions act simultaneously without a unique solution from static equilibrium equations alone, making precise alignment and reconfiguration more difficult. In contrast, the following concept outlines a statically determinate demonstrator designed for the deep drawing of cylindrical cups. A system is considered statically determinate when all potential movements are fully constrained by distinct and calculable reaction forces or bearings, with no redundant constraints. Figure 1 illustrates the proposed demonstrator, highlighting the support configuration for the die, blank holder, and punch.

Figure 1. A schematic representation of the structural configuration of the deep drawing demonstrator, along with the bearing reactions of the mount for the blank holder and the die. This schematic includes the compensation of misalignment Δa , during the tooling closure.

In this tool concept, both the blank holder and the punch are granted limited lateral freedom, perpendicular to the press stroke, prior to tool closure. Upon closing the die, the blank holder is guided by the outer surface of the die, effectively eliminating lateral degrees of freedom. Simultaneously, the punch self-aligns coaxially with the die, ensuring proper centering without relying on overconstrained guidance elements. The design of this demonstrator is provided in a subsequent section of the paper.

3. Methodology

3.1. Material

The material employed in this study is DC05, a mild low-carbon steel widely used in forming applications, with a nominal sheet thickness of 2.75 mm. All samples used for material characterization and deep drawing experiments were extracted from sheet cuts belonging to the same production batch to ensure material consistency. For uniaxial tensile testing, specimens were laser-cut in three orientations relative to the rolling direction: 0° , 45° , and 90° . Each specimen had a gauge length of 40 mm and a width of 10.08 mm. Tensile tests were conducted using a Zwick Roell Z250 universal testing machine. Strain measurements were performed using a digital image correlation (DIC) system (GOM Aramis 12M) along with GOM Correlate software.

Two tests were conducted per orientation. The resulting true stress–strain curves from the uniaxial tests are presented in Figure 2. To evaluate anisotropy, width strain was additionally recorded, enabling the estimation of r -values in the plastic strain range of 10% to 20%. The average r -values, as well as yield and ultimate tensile strengths, are summarized in Table 1.

Figure 2. True stress and strain curves of DC05 with 0°, 45° and 90° orientation to the rolling direction

Table 1. Summary of the results with the average values (bold) for each orientation

	Orientation to rolling direction		
	0°	45°	90°
Yield strength [MPa]	195,61 (194,5 - 196,72)	199,29 (199,2 - 199,38)	197,07 (196,62 - 197,52)
Tensile strength [MPa]	290,34 (290,12 - 290,56)	302,12 (301,99 - 302,24)	290,46 (290,42 - 290,51)
r -value [-]	1,277 (1.254 - 1,3)	1,036 (1.033 - 1,039)	1,5655 (1.552 - 1,579)

Compared to standard values for DC05, the experimental results indicate notable deviations. The average yield strength of 197.32 MPa exceeds the typical reference value of 180 MPa, while the r_{90} value of 1.5655 suggests reduced planar anisotropy compared to the commonly reported value of 1.9 [6]. For the deep drawing experiments, circular blanks with a diameter of 92.5 mm were punched from the same batch of DC05 material used for characterization.

3.2. Experimental Setup

To validate the finite element (FE) simulation model for the deep drawing of cylindrical cups, experimental tests were performed, with a focus on wall thickness distribution influenced by the anisotropic material behavior and the alignment of the blank. Additionally, stroke and forming force were monitored during the drawing process for further comparison. After forming, wall thickness measurements were taken along the cup circumference at a defined height.

The deep drawing demonstrator, previously utilized by Geuke [7], was mounted onto a ZWICK/Roell Z250 universal testing machine, which has a maximum load capacity of 250 kN (see Figure 3). In this setup, punch displacement was actuated and controlled via the machine's lower traverse, driven by servomotoric spindles. A constant stroke rate of 4 mm/s over a travel distance of 41 mm was employed.

Punch displacement was recorded using a potentiometric displacement sensor (Burster Type 8313-100) with a measurement range of 0–100 mm. Forming force was measured using the Z250's built-in load cell (GTM 250 kN, Type K). The blank holder force was monitored via the hydraulic cylinder pressure, which was regulated to 16 kN at 63 bar. All sensor data were logged using a Gantner Instruments Q.Station X data acquisition system.

Figure 3. View of the mounted deep drawing demonstrator with hydraulic actuated blank holder, load cell for punch force and displacement transducer for punch displacement (left) and cut view of the deep drawing tool (right)

The tool geometry was designed for forming 2.75 mm thick DC05 blanks. The die featured an inner diameter of 66.7 mm and a corner radius of 5.7 mm. The blank holder mount (upper grey plate in Figure 3) had an inner diameter of 139.97 mm, slightly exceeding the die's outer diameter of 139.92 mm, thereby providing lateral guidance and enabling coaxial alignment of the punch and blank holder with the die. The punch was aligned via a 60.02 mm bore, and its outer diameter measured 60.01 mm, with a nose radius of 11 mm. This configuration produced a nominal gap of 3.35 mm between the punch and die.

Circular blanks were centered within the die, and their dimensions were verified using a caliper prior to forming. Post-process wall thickness measurements were conducted using a GOM Atos Q 3D scanner and evaluated with Zeiss Inspect software. The simulation results were analyzed using the same software. In both cases, wall thickness was measured at defined vertical positions along the cup wall, starting from the cup base (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Illustration of the reference heights used to evaluate the thickness across the circumference of the cup and orientation of the angle α

3.3. Simulation Modell

The finite element (FE) software Simufact Forming (Hexagon AB) was used to simulate the deep drawing process described in the experimental setup. The simulation model geometry was based on the exact tool and blank dimensions used in the experiments (see Figures 3 and 5a). The die, punch, and pintles were modelled as rigid bodies. The pintles applied a total force of 16 kN to the blank holder. Hexahedral elements were used to mesh both the blank and the blank holder. The blank, modelled with a mesh size of 1.0 mm, consisted of 55,480 elements. The blank holder, made of tool steel (1.2379), was meshed with a 1.5 mm element size, resulting in 72,030 elements (see Figures 5b and 5c).

Figure 5. a) tool setup for FEM simulation with additional pintles for applying the blank holder force b) meshed blank and c) meshed blank holder.

Simufact Forming employs the MSC.Marc solver, which is based on an implicit finite element method. In the absence of friction test data, the friction coefficient (μ) was adopted from literature. A study by Recklin [8] on deep drawing processes reported a typical range of $\mu = 0.1$ – 0.2 . For this study, a constant friction coefficient of $\mu = 0.12$ was applied according to Coulomb's Law [9]. To capture the anisotropic plastic behaviour of DC05, the Hill'48 yield criterion was used, parameterized by the r-values obtained from uniaxial tensile tests (see Table 1) [10]. The material's flow curve, derived from the experimental stress–strain data (see Figure 2), was fitted using a combined Swift/Krupkowski hardening law [11] with $K_0 = 510.7$ MPa, $\epsilon_0 = 0.0041$ and $n = 0.231$.

This study investigates the effect of coaxial alignment between the punch and die on the wall thickness distribution of deep drawn cups. In the experimental setup (see Figure 1), coaxial alignment is achieved through guided retraction of the blank holder. Accordingly, a first simulation was conducted under coaxial alignment conditions and compared with the experimental results in terms of circumferential wall thickness distribution.

Subsequently, simulations were performed with deliberate coaxial misalignment between the punch and die. Misalignment was introduced by displacing the punch along the x-axis (rolling direction, RD) and y-axis (transverse direction, TD). Two displacement magnitudes were investigated: 5% and 15% of the punch–die gap width (see Table 2), to also assess the influence of material anisotropy under misaligned conditions.

Table 2. Displacement of the punch for the simulations

Description	Displacement [mm]	
	x	y
Center	0.0	0.0
RD5	0.1675	0.0
TD5	0.0	0.1675
RD15	0.5025	0.0
TD15	0.0	0.5025

4. Results

The wall thickness distribution along the circumference of the deep drawn cups was evaluated at multiple heights from the cup base (see Figure 4a and 4b). Figure 6 shows a representative thickness mapping of a cup’s mid-section, beginning from the corner radius near the base (2.57 mm) and extending to the wall, where thickening reaches up to 3.24 mm.

Figure 6. Mapping of thickness on the cup resulting of center simulation

A comparison between the experimental cup and the simulated center cup shows close agreement in wall thickness at heights of 20 mm and 22.5 mm (see Figure 7). At 17.5 mm, the average wall thickness in the experiment was 2.712 mm—0.045 mm lower than the simulation. At 20 mm and 22.5 mm, the differences were 0.012 mm and 0.005 mm, respectively. This indicates that the simulation successfully captures the anisotropic behavior of DC05, although with a slight overestimation of the wall thickness.

Figure 7. Comparison of experimental and center cup at all three heights

Punch displacement in the rolling direction (x-axis) was simulated at 5% (RD5) and 15% (RD15) of the nominal punch–die gap. The resulting circumferential wall thickness profiles at all heights are shown in Figure 8. For both cases, local maxima appear near 180°, opposite the direction of misalignment. These peaks differ from the ones at 45° and 315°.

For RD15, at 22.5mm, the thickness ranged from 2.804 mm to 3.066 mm, with a total variation of 0.262 mm. For RD5, this variation was smaller, at 0.063 mm. Average wall thickness values for RD5 and RD15 at heights of 20 mm and 22.5 mm deviated between -0.018 mm and +0.007 mm compared to the experiment. These results indicate increased thickness variation and reduced uniformity under higher misalignment in the rolling direction.

Figure 8. Comparison of experimental, RD5 and RD15 cup at all three heights.

Simulations with punch offsets in the transverse direction (TD5 and TD15) show a shift in wall thickness maxima toward 270°, consistent with the punch movement direction (see Figure 9). At TD5, small shifts were observed at 17.5 mm and 20 mm heights. For example, at 20 mm, the variation was 0.073 mm for TD5, 0.076 mm for the center cup, and 0.087 mm for RD5.

At TD15, thickness variations increased substantially. At 22.5 mm height, the minimum and maximum thicknesses were 2.825 mm and 3.064 mm, respectively a range of 0.239 mm. The average thickness deviations for TD5 and TD15 at 20 and 22.5 mm were between -0.019 mm and -0.007 mm, while the deviation at 17.5 mm was greater, at -0.049 mm and -0.038 mm, respectively.

Figure 9. Comparison of experimental, TD5 and TD15 cup at all three heights.

Figure 10a presents a comprehensive comparison of all simulated and experimental cups at a height of 22.5 mm, identified as the position with the most pronounced wall thickness variations. This is further illustrated in Figure 10b, which summarizes the mean wall thickness

along with the respective minimum and maximum values for each configuration. The RD15 and TD15 cases exhibit the greatest deviations, with thickness values ranging from 2.85 mm to 3.066 mm and 2.825 mm to 3.064 mm, respectively. Despite these variations, the average wall thicknesses for RD15 and TD15 remain slightly higher than the experimental reference, at 2.980 mm and 2.978 mm. These findings confirm that higher misalignments, especially in the rolling direction, significantly impair wall thickness uniformity.

a)

b)

Figure 10. a) Comparison of all cups at 22.5 mm of height b) Mean thickness at all heights for all cup configurations. Red error bars indicate the respective minimum and maximum wall thicknesses.

In addition to wall thickness distribution, the cup concentricity and roundness of the deep drawn cups were analysed to further assess geometric quality (see Table 3.).

Table 3. Resulting cup concentricity and roundness of the cups at the different heights

Description	Cup concentricity [mm]	roundness [mm] at each height		
		17.5	20	22.5
Exp	0.08	0.02	0.06	0.15
Center	0.0	0.03	0.06	0.14
RD5	0.32	0.04	0.06	0.18
TD5	0.05	0.03	0.05	0.15
RD15	0.96	0.04	0.07	0.23
TD15	0.94	0.04	0.06	0.21

Cup concentricity increases significantly with higher misalignment, particularly in RD15 and TD15, where values approach ~ 1 mm. In comparison to the cup concentricity, the roundness deviations remain relatively small across all conditions, staying below 0.25 mm. While no substantial increase is observed, a slight trend toward higher roundness deviations can be seen with increasing punch–die misalignment.

5. Discussion

The results of this study clearly demonstrate the significant influence of coaxial misalignment between the punch and die on wall thickness distribution in deep drawn cup geometries. Using the non-conventional deep drawing demonstrator (see Figures 1 and 3), a symmetric cup was successfully formed under coaxial conditions, validating the tool's alignment concept through both experiment and simulation. The key design features, lateral degrees of freedom for punch and blank holder, outer die guidance, and self-alignment during closure, enable compensation for initial misalignments and help maintain geometric quality.

In contrast, conventional tooling systems, typically statically overdetermined, do not permit such alignment correction. When misalignment occurs, particularly in rigid configurations, it leads to circumferential shifts in wall thickness, as illustrated in Figures 8 and 9. This results in increased local extrema, shifts in the center of mass, and uneven material flow.

In addition to thickness variations, the measurements of cup concentricity and roundness provided further insight into the geometric consequences of misalignment. With growing misalignment, the cup concentricity reaches values close to 1 mm in the RD15 and TD15 configurations. Roundness deviations remained relatively small across all conditions (below 0.25 mm), though a slight increase was observed with higher misalignments.

Particularly under a 15% misalignment condition, the minimum punch–die gap narrows to 2.85 mm, just 0.1 mm above the blank's thickness, raising the risk of unintended ironing. This promotes asymmetric contact forces and elastic deformation of the punch, resulting in localized stresses and potential uneven tool wear. A 5% misalignment does not lead to ironing but still impairs circumferential wall thickness and concentricity, degrading part quality.

These findings underscore the importance of precise coaxial alignment during deep drawing tool setup. In industrial practice, frequent product or material changes increase the likelihood of alignment errors, which are difficult to detect without specialized inspection. The non-conventional tool concept presented in this study mitigates the impact of such errors, enhancing process resilience and supporting robust production with fewer defective parts, even under variable conditions.

Based on the observed results, misalignments up to 5% of the punch–die gap caused only moderate deviations in wall thickness (<0.07 mm) and roundness (<0.18 mm). In contrast, 15% misalignment led to significantly larger variations, including thickness deviations >0.25 mm and concentricity errors near 1 mm. While the acceptability of these deviations depends on specific part requirements, these results offer a basis for estimating alignment tolerance thresholds in similar deep drawing applications.

6 Conclusions

This study has demonstrated the pronounced influence of coaxial misalignment between the punch and die on the geometric quality and wall thickness distribution of deep drawn cup-shaped components. Through combined experimental validation and finite element simulations, it was

shown that even relatively small misalignments can significantly alter the thickness profile, increasing the likelihood of defects and accelerating tool wear due to asymmetric loading conditions.

The non-conventional tool concept introduced in this work, featuring lateral degrees of freedom and guided alignment near the forming zone, proved effective in compensating for misalignment during tool closure. This approach not only reduces the negative effects associated with geometric deviation but also simplifies tool setup, lowering the required expertise and time for reconfiguration.

The findings suggest that such tooling concepts can substantially improve process robustness, extend tool life, and enhance production resilience, especially in environments with frequent product or material changes. Future implementations may further explore integration into automated setup procedures and broader applications in multi-stage forming operations. In addition, future research could investigate how initial misalignments in the first forming stage affect subsequent forming stages, as early geometric deviations may propagate or amplify in multistage cup production.

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